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Executive summary

The current deliverable (D3.5 - Peer review report) is part of WayOut WP3 (Evaluation Framework of exit programmes) and presents a report based on the results gathered in online questionnaires and semi-structured interviews applied to previously identified exit programmes. A total of 14 exit workers agreed to be interviewed by one of the consortium partners, and after summarising or transcribing the interviews, aggregated results were developed and are presented in the current report.

Results from the online questionnaires and interviews show that exit programmes share similarities in domains such as the team composition and duration of the intervention, while other aspect may differ according to the programme goals, such as the role played by ideology, the type of intervention, or the contact approach. The comparison between the different programmes' evaluation attributes also allowed the authors to flag aspects of the programmes that, in general, may need improvement, such as the use of risk and needs assessment tools and the evaluation of the programmes.

1. Introduction

The current deliverable aims to review current exit strategies and programmes being implemented in Europe. Following the literature review done in the current Work Package, as well as the development of a proposal for evaluating Exit programmes and the respective manual, the current deliverable aggregates quantitative and qualitative data related to identified exit programmes that participated in the evaluation.

2. Evaluation of exit programmes

The current evaluation of exit programmes was done following the procedures detailed on D3.3 Evaluation framework user manual. A shared Excel spreadsheet was initially created considering the programmes mapped under D3.4. Partners showed their intention to evaluate programmes based on their networks (i.e., closer contact with the contact person) and interest on the programmes. From a total of twenty-six programmes that included in this list, contacts were identified and made in twenty-two cases. 4 out of the twenty-two contacts did not answer to the first contact, and 2 declined the invitation for an evaluation interview. Of the remaining sixteen contacts, 14 agreed to schedule and conduct an interview with one of the WayOut project partners.

The following programmes were evaluated:

- Back on track (Denmark), run by the Danish Prison and Probation Service;
- Exit- Deutschland (Germany), run by Society Democratic Culture;
- Just X Berlin - Prevention and deradicalisation in Berlin prisons (Germany), run by Violence Prevention Network, Denkzeit, Nexus;
- PräRaDEx - Prevention of radicalisation, distancing from extremism (Germany), run by CJD-Nord in cooperation with the Ministry of Justice in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania;
- Terrorist Wing Vught (The Netherlands), run by the Penitentiary Institute in Vught;
- Aggredi programme (Finland), run by HelsinkiMissio;
- Kick-Off - Prevention and deradicalisation in the prison and probation services (Germany), run by the Turkish community in Schleswig-Holstein;
- Kurswechsel - Ausstiegsarbeit rechts (Germany), run by CJD-Nord (Hamburg);
- KuBiBe - Kultur Bildung Beratung (Culture Education Mentoring) (Germany), run by AMA e.V. / Legato;
- Radicalisation Prevention and Deradicalisation in Prison and Probation (Germany), run by Violence Prevention Network (VPN);
- PREVENT (Germany), run by Violence Prevention Network (VPN);
- Exit from jihadist ideology (France), run by Association l'Entre 2; and
- The disengagement/reengagement path (Belgium), run by Centre d'Aide et de Prise en charge de toute personne concernée par les Extrémismes et Radicalismes Violents (CAPREV).
- Norwegian Mentoring Programme (Norway), run by “Utekontakten” social department

(Bergen Municipality) in close collaboration with Regional Centre on Violence, Traumatic Stress and Suicide Prevention, Region West and West Police district.

Considering the pandemic situation that is affecting the world (partner countries being no exception), all interviews took place using online platforms. All interviewees agreed/signed an informed consent form. Some participants agreed to record the interview while other did not. This variability led to different formats of data, ranging from transcripts of entire interviews to a summary of key aspects discussed with interviewees. Therefore, the current output was built based on these information blocks, trying to give similar emphasis to the different programmes, independent of the amount of information obtained from the interviews. Moreover, it is our goal here to personalise as little as possible, but instead provide general results from the data that was gathered, therefore protecting the programmes' identity when presenting specific results.

3. General Overview of the evaluated programmes

3.1. Geographical Distribution

Considering the geographical distribution of the evaluated programmes, 8 programmes were evaluated in Germany, while the other 6 programmes were spread across different countries with one programme on each of the following countries: Denmark, France, Finland, Belgium, Norway and The Netherlands.

The higher numbers in Germany are related to the partnership presence in the country (with both Violence Prevention Network - VPN - and the Bremen Ministry of Justice as project partners). Furthermore, it relates to the variety of programmes available in Germany, ranging from civil-society-led initiatives, structural cooperations and government-led initiatives. Due to the federal structure and decentralised approach to P/CVE in the country, the consortium assessed an inclusion of a richer sample to illustrate the variety of programs as beneficial for the project evaluation. Lastly, the inclusion of long-standing expertise in the area of right-wing extremism was of interest for the assessment.

3.2. Quantitative analysis

An online survey was shared with the participants. The initial idea was that this first contact with the programmes would allow partners to understand key attributes of the programmes (in general) and therefore be able to prepare the interview, highlighting some of the topics that stand out in the questionnaire.

Despite the low response rate (only 7 representatives of the programmes answered the questionnaire), some tendencies are interesting to be analysed. Programmes were mostly described as tailormade interventions (6), but also as a cognitive skills programme (3) and a psychosocial intervention (3). Other answers include “As a set of creative, cultural and recreational activities”, “As an education course”, both with one answer. Additional descriptions were allowed, and respondents added options such as “Mentoring programme” and “pedagogical/behavioural approach with a focus on life goals”.

When asked about the involvement of other actors in the programme, participant's family and social networks can be highlighted (5 answers); followed by Religious experts (3), Influential personalities (3), and former violent extremists / gang members (2).

Regarding contact approach, the role of ideology, and programmes' implementation, results can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Communication, ideology and implementation of exit programme

Although with some nuances, the displayed results show that programmes apply some active communication strategies trying to reach out potential participants. These strategies will be explored in more detail in our qualitative analysis. The ideological component appears to be a divisive topic for the programmes, being both not relevant and relevant depending on the programmes goals, and most interventions will work on a one-on-one basis.

Other questions related with the exit programmes were asked and answers were provided on a likert-type scale with 6 points (1 - Strongly Disagree; 2 - Disagree; 3 - Slightly Disagree; 4 - Slightly Agree; 5 - Agree; 6 - Strongly Agree). Results for each item are presented in Table 1, showing the weighted average response for each question.

	Weighted Average
Design of the programme took into consideration up-to-date scientific literature.	4,71
The implementation team is comprised of skilled professionals.	5,29
The implementation team is multidisciplinary.	5,29
Participation in the programme is voluntary.	5
Duration of the intervention programme is appropriate.	5,43
There is a strong collaboration between our organisation and other agencies (police, prison, community organisations, etc.).	5,43

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Tools are used to assess participants needs.	4,86
Tools are used to draw an individual intervention plan to address participants' needs.	4,86
Tools are used to assess participants risk level.	4,14
Tools are used to draw and individual intervention plan addressing participants risks.	4,14
Programme effectiveness mechanisms are being accessed	4,71
Post-intervention monitorisation actions are implemented.	4,14
Former participants are followed-up	4,29
The programme is connected to a long-term aftercare plan.	4,14
A clear evaluation framework is implemented to assess the programme.	4,43
Participants are involved in the programme's evaluation.	4,71
Stakeholders are involved in the programme's evaluation.	4,86
Evaluation results are used for decisions on project funding.	4,71
Evaluation results are used for decisions on project continuity.	4,86
Cost-effectiveness of the intervention is assessed.	3,71
Programme evaluation reports are produced and available to national authorities.	4,43
Programme evaluation reports are produced and publicly available.	3,29

As can be seen, items that reach a higher average value are related with the configuration of the team, duration of the programme and multiagency cooperation. Lower values are obtained in items related with risk assessment implementation and usage of results for intervention programmes. Also, based on these quantitative results it is unlikely that programmes assess the cost-effectiveness of the interventions as well as have and/or provide to the wide public evaluation reports.

Still on a 6-point scale, respondents were asked about fine-tuning the intervention programme. On average, participants stated that the intervention programmes are fine-tuned ($M= 5,14$), and that this fine-tuning occurs using inputs from the programme evaluation ($M= 4,43$) or are made according to new theoretical developments in the field ($M= 4,43$).

3.3. Qualitative analysis

Despite the efforts in collecting quantitative data previously shown, the nature of the assessment that was created relied mostly on qualitative evaluation of the programmes through a semi-structured interview. In fact, the centrality of the interview in the process was acknowledged from the beginning of the development of D3.2 - Exit interventions evaluation framework report, with the online questionnaire playing a more complementary role and allowing participants to adapt the interview questions accordingly (i.e., exploring some themes highlighted by the online questionnaires' answers). That may explain partners' approach when contacting the potential interviewees and why more participants agreed with being interviewed, despite it is more time-consuming.

In this subsection, answers from the 14 programmes evaluated will be combined and attributes of exit programmes (as developed in previous WayOut deliverables) will be described based on aggregated results. To allow for a comparison of the data received, an excel spreadsheet was created using the template previously shared with the partners (cf. Annex IV of D3.3. Evaluation framework user manual). Data features were then inserted which allowed a faster comparison of

data elements between the different interviews. Consequently, some attributes benefit from larger data features, while others received less elements.

Characteristics of the programme

Some of the programmes that were included in the interviews are organised around participants' biography, with the use of one-on-one counselling work or mentoring. Families are usually contacted (to know more about the participant, as part of a tailormade approach) or even involved in the intervention (in sessions with the intervention team). Formers/deradicalised individuals can also be included, usually under supervision and as a role model to the current participants. Other programmes are characterised by group interventions, that can be as diverse as education actions (e.g., teaching democracy), or group dynamics moderated by the trainers in which participants define targets and determine what they want to change and how to achieve these changes.

Type of intervention

The evaluated programmes will mostly fall in the category of individual intervention programmes (some with a focus on religious radicalisation, others with a focus on right-wing extremism, some applying mentoring, others favouring psychotherapeutic rehabilitation). However, some programmes may also encompass a systemic approach (e.g., LEGATO; Exchange Brandenburg) complemented by on-on-one interventions according to the risk level of the participants (or even two-on-one intervention, with two members of the staff per participant).

Team skills and composition

Teams implementing exit programmes are multidisciplinary, with a combination of different specialists depending on the programme goals. Most common education and background of team members appear to be in the fields of criminology and law, political science, and education/pedagogy. Other professionals from psychology, security/police, social work, healthcare, Islamic studies, social anthropology and gender studies are also common in these intervention programmes. Therefore, experience and competence of these professionals' ranges from the fields of clinical social work, mental health, violence, counselling/systemic therapy, forced migration and refugee health, to the fields of risk-assessment, theology/religion and cultural diversity, radicalisation and hate-crimes.

In terms of dimension, teams can have as little as 2 persons (e.g., Back on Track), but usually involve five to seven professionals (e.g., KickOff; PREVENT; Agreedi). A large group of professionals can also be found, especially when municipalities are involved (e.g., Mentoring programme of the Bergen Municipality in Norway).

The involvement of former extremists in the team is foreseen by a few programmes (e.g., exit Deutschland; L'ENTRE 2), as well as the involvement of families in the programme. The need for initial and continuous training is also mentioned, as previous personal experience on the area of action is valued. The programmes applying group interventions also highlight the benefits of having trainers with consulting experience with groups.

Considering the multidisciplinary nature of the teams, in one case it is mentioned that the

assignment of a team member to a case is done based on the needs' assessment (e.g., CAPREV). Skills of the team members may include the ability to make contact, be authentic and show real empathy.

Contact approach

The kind of contact approach (i.e., active vs passive) varies across programmes as the quantitative data already showed. This means that some programmes are totally passive in their contact approach - that is, they do not approach potential participants directly but instead rely on potential clients' interest in the programme - while other programmes establish contact and have preliminary calls with potential participants or even write letters to potential participants (inmates). The active contact approach can also result in potential participants being referred to be programme by other professionals (particularly in the prison and probation contexts). A third type of contact approach (a mediated approach) was also found, with information about the programmes reaching potential participant through families or even with families bringing participants (in the community) to the programme.

Type of participation

All programmes interviewed favour a voluntary participation. Even though some participants can join the programmes after a judicial mandate, it is recognised that a willingness to join the programmes is a pre-requisite for the programme's success. Of course, voluntary participation has its own drawbacks, and contrary to mandatory participation (that will allow the intervention to start as soon as there is a decision in that regard) can result in months or even years of effort to engage participants (such as in the case of prisons, where active communication efforts can be made to attract participants but do not guarantee their immediate entry at the programme). However, participation is voluntary in a vast majority of the programmes, meaning that there is no possibility to sanction members of the target group if they do not agree to participate or want to withdraw from the programme.

Role of Ideology

The role played by ideology in the evaluated programmes are usually limited, with some interviewees stating that ideological discussions can be counterproductive (i.e. confrontation can damage relationship, needs to be carefully introduced). More common is the exploration of why the participant felt attracted by those extreme ideologies. Consequently, programmes tend to intervene in the realms of biographical work and disengagement (i.e., trying to achieve behavioural change). A biographical approach to radicalisation and deradicalisation/disengagement appears to be common and focus on the life course of these individuals, their daily experiences and perspectives of change, their values (what they see as important), while trying to interpret their narratives about their past, present and future (Roberts, 2002, cit in Sieckelinck et al., 2019). However, there are exception in which ideology plays a main role. This is true in the programmes that aim at deradicalise participants. In these cases, additional training on ideology may be offered to the implementation team. This team may also include religious experts/leaders.

Duration

Length of the intervention programmes range from several months to a few years. Programmes applying a group or pedagogical intervention may have a shorter, better-defined implementation period (six/seven months), while individual programmes have a longer duration (from one to three years), with some programmes' duration depending on participants willingness or the length of the sentence.

Risk and needs assessment

Risk and needs assessment, that is, the assessment of participants' needs and risks at any stage of the exit intervention, are performed by some of the assessed programmes. Four out of the 14 programmes report no use of risk and needs assessment. Considering the remaining 10, four use their own developed strategies such as:

- A risk (and credibility) assessment of participants to protect staff and avoid attempts to infiltrate people in the project (exit Deutschland);
- An anamnesis¹ sheet developed for the programme (LEGATO);
- Assessment of the risk regarding the work relation with the client, the safety of team members, as well as the risk for the client during the programme (e.g. in his environment, the circumstances surrounding his situation) (NEXUS); and
- Whether an individual is suitable for a group programme or if someone is already so highly radicalized, that they need one-on-one sessions (Exchange Brandenburg).

The remaining six exit programmes use published needs/risk assessment tools such as:

- KISSeS-strategy², a framework developed by Prof. Kurt Möller in order to identify clients' needs and subsequently to strengthen and stabilise relevant components/ factors (PREVENT);
- Level of service Inventory (Back on Track);
- Hexagon tool³ to assess participants needs (CAPREV);
- VERA-2R and sometimes the HCR-20 and SAAP-prof (Terrorist Wing, PI Vught);
- NOORAPPLI 3D⁴ (Bouzar & Bénézech, 2019), used by the project implemented by L'ENTRE 2;
- Terrorist Radicalization Assessment Protocol-18 (TRAP-18), Spousal Assault Risk Assessment (SARA); and the Assessment of Honour Based Violence (PATRIARCH), used by the Mentoring Scheme in Norway.

¹ Anamnesis (from the Greek *ana* - bring back - and *mnesis* - memory -, is a starting point in the clinical diagnosis of a person, encompassing a clinical history of all symptoms described by a patient. In this case, it might represent an adaptation of an anamnesis form to the context of the Exit programme.

² More information, available in German, can be found here: <https://www.eiz-rostock.de/projekte/land-sicht-demokratiegestaltung-innovativ-qualifizieren/land-in-sicht-weiterbildung-2018/kisses-strategie/>

³ More information is available here:

https://nirn.fpg.unc.edu/sites/nirn.fpg.unc.edu/files/imce/documents/NIRN%20Hexagon%20Discussion%20Analysis%20Tool_September2020_1.pdf

⁴ Neutralizing Online and Offline Radicalization. 3D refers to the three evaluated dimensions leading to an emotional, relational or ideological cognitive change.

Monitoring / Follow-up / Aftercare

Follow-up of participants occurs in some of the evaluated programmes (seven out of 14). Some interviewees state that participants return to the programme (usually when facing personal challenges) but this return is voluntary (the programme keeps the door open). A more structured aftercare is also available such as in the case of the Terrorist Wing, PI Vught programme in which various organisations (municipalities, probation, law enforcement, social work, and so on) are involved, or in the case of the Exchange Brandenburg programme in which the team supports the client for about one additional year after release from prison.

Evaluation

In terms of evaluation of exit programmes, our results are aligned with Koehler's (2017), since we observed a very unstructured (or even non-existent) evaluation procedure. Interviewees usually refer to qualitative indicators of evaluation, such as the more subjective perceptions that participants have evolved favourably throughout the implementation of the programme (i.e., reducing violent behaviour, abandoning ideological extreme positions), but have little to no evidence that the programme worked (i.e., quantitatively). However, some programmes use indicators such as recidivism (e.g., CAPREV; Mentoring Scheme) to evaluate programme's success. Others (Terrorist Wing, PI Vught), consider that although recidivism is the only real measure of success, recidivism rates of these inmates tend to be low even without interventions, and therefore success of the intervention is difficult to be measured. The evaluation of the exit programmes can also be connected, particularly when talking about the success of the interventions in terms of promoting individual change, to the risk and needs assessment tools that are being used. For instance, the KISSeS-strategy will monitor individual changes in the level of satisfaction of relevant needs and the effects that practitioners' interventions had in this regard.

When available, evaluation reports are usually in the national languages, such as in the case of Back of Track programme. Some exit interventions were also evaluated by external organisations (such as the Camino Institut or RadarEurope). Cost-effectiveness evaluations are not performed and mostly seen as not relevant for these programmes.

4. Conclusions / Discussion

The current deliverable tried to aggregate the data received from an online questionnaire and semi-structured interviews with programme managers/members of the implementation team of exit programmes in Europe. A total of 14 exit workers were interviewed, which allowed us to deepen our understanding regarding the characteristics of these programmes, its duration, contact with other organisations, use of risk and needs assessment, and evaluation, among other attributes previously identified.

As a main conclusion, despite the challenging tasks of aggregating data from the interviews and trying to generate some meaning from different data sources, exit programmes appear to have similar characteristics, particularly in what concerns the duration of the programmes and the characteristics of the staff incorporating the implementation teams. However, other aspects may

be very different from one intervention to another, such as the use of validated need and risk assessment tools, the role played by ideology, the type of intervention (individual vs group; mentoring vs educational), or the contact approach (passive vs active).

Duration of the programmes, aligned with the characteristics of these interventions, shows us how complex the behavioural (and sometimes cognitive) changes are and the difficulty in reaching them, even when these interventions are individualised and applied by multidisciplinary teams comprised of specialised staff.

Results regarding the use of risk and needs assessment show that substantial efforts need to be made in what concerns the training of exit practitioners in risk and needs assessment use and even awareness raising on their importance. In fact, we argue that risk and needs assessment should be seen as an inseparable part of the Exit programme's implementation process. The assessment of risk and needs will allow exit programmes to adapt their programmes, measure their impact and improve the security of their staff, by understanding the individual risks and needs of participants. In what regards the evaluation of the exit programmes, the qualitative evaluations (based on practitioners' perceptions) performed by some of the assessed programmes can pose a serious threat in case the programmes need to provide evidence regarding their effectiveness in order to raise funds for their continuity. The use of risk and needs assessment is important not only to measure changes in participants along the intervention but also to adapt the length and content of the intervention to the participants' needs and risks, saving time and resources with participants at low risk while directing more resources to the ones a higher risk (cf. Monahan & Skeem, 2016). In fact, while almost all programmes will describe themselves as a tailor-made intervention, some concerns may be raised on how can interventions be adapted to the individual needs and risks of violent extremists if the mentioned needs and risks are not assessed? Therefore, individual intervention programmes (instead of tailor-made interventions) would describe better some of the programmes assessed and these results, while having its own limitation, reinforce the idea that a more structured approach to needs and risk assessment may be needed in some of these interventions.

In what concerns the follow-up and aftercare of participants, results show that there is still space for improving the current practices. While some programmes stay in contact with former participants and even try to put them in contact with their mentor/counselor in case they return searching for help, other programmes have no follow-up or aftercare strategy, which may result in a lack of support to the former participant in times of personal problems. Here, the resources a programme has can play an important role, with limited resources leading to the impossibility of following up former participants. Cases are also likely to be handed over to other institutions, since reintegration is a long process, which may result in a loss of contact and relationship with the client.

The method used in the current report has some limitations. Namely, interviews were performed by different elements of the project partners, with a diverse background and relationship with the different programmes. Since interviews were mostly done in the national partner languages or in English, issues related with interpretation and translation may occur. The same potential for misinterpretation applies to the online questionnaire that was only available in English. It is also important to state that even though 59% of the identified programmes were evaluated, the disparities in the method and the qualitative approach followed do not allow a generalisation of

the results and conclusions to other programmes.

Despite the limitations of the methods used to collect the data presented on the current report, the implementation of the interviews represented an opportunity for WayOut partners to implement the developed evaluation strategy, approximating to the practical and real world the theoretical exercise that led to the creation of such a strategy. In general, the semi-structured interview succeeds in the collection of data elements that allow a comparison of different projects, allowing the authors to reach some general conclusions and recommendations.

5. References

- Bouzar, D., & Bénézech, M. (2019). Practical Guide of Assessment of Disengagement from Jihadist Violent Extremism: Indicators of deradicalization. *Journal of Current Medical Research and Opinion*, 02(10), 256-284. <https://doi.org/10.15520/jcmro.v2i10.211>
- Koehler, D. (2017). *Structural Quality Standards for work to intervene with and counter violent extremism*.
- Monahan, J., & Skeem, J. L. (2016). Risk Assessment in Criminal Sentencing. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 12(1), 489-513. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-021815-092945>
- Sieckelinck, S., Sikkens, E., San, M. Van, Kotnis, S., & De Winter, M. (2019). Transitional journeys into and out of extremism. A biographical approach. *Studies in Conflict and Terrorism*, 42(7), 662-682. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610X.2017.1407075>

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